

Product Info					Q = QUESTION
	Q10	Q11	Q12	Q13	P = PARTICIPANT
P1	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games, Games for health	Mobile devices	Mobile app stores	Unity, Own technology	
P2	Corporate training games	Browsers	Own website	Unity, Unreal, Blender, Godot	
P3	Educational games	PlayTable	Own distribution	Unity	
P4	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games, Advergams	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Own website	Unity, Unreal	
P5	Entertainment games, Educational games, Advergams, Simulators, AI apps and platforms	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity	
P6	Entertainment games	Computer, Console	Digital download stores	Unity	
P7	Entertainment games	Mobile devices	Mobile app stores	Unity	
P8	Entertainment games, Educational games, Advergams, Simulators, AI apps and platforms	Mobile devices, Computer, Console, Augmented reality, VR	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Own website, Online gaming portals	Unity, Unreal, Godot	
P9	Entertainment games	Computer, Console	Publishers, Digital Download Stores	Unity, Unreal, Blender, Gamemaker	
P10	Entertainment games	Computador, Console	Publishers, Digital download stores, Online gaming portals	Unity	
P11	Entertainment games, Art outsourcing	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console, Augmented reality	We do not distribute games.	Unity, Unreal, Blender, Godot	
P12	Entertainment games, Simulators	Computer, Browsers	Digital download stores	Unreal, Game Maker Studio 2	

P13	Educational games, Corporate training games, Games for health	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Own website	Unity, Blender, HTML5
P14	Entertainment games	Computer	Digital download stores	Blender
P15	Entertainment games, Adult content games	Computer	Digital download stores	Fusion
P16	Entertainment games	Computer, Console	Publishers, Digital Download Stores	Construct
P17	Entertainment games	VR	Digital download stores	Unity, Unreal
P18	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games, Advergaming, Games for well-being	Mobile devices, Browsers, Consoles, Augmented reality, Virtual reality and Mixed reality	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity, Unreal, Construct
P19	Entertainment games	Computer	Digital download stores	Construct
P20	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games, Advergaming, Simulators	Mobile devices, Computers, Browsers, Augmented reality	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity, Unreal, Construct, Blender
P21	Entertainment games, Advergaming	Mobile devices, Computer, Console	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity
P22	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Console	Publishers, Mobile app stores	Unity, Godot
P23	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Console	Publishers, Digital Download Stores	Unity
P24	Entertainment games, Educational games	Mobile devices, Computer, Console	Digital download stores	Unity, Godot
P25	Entertainment games	Computer	Digital download stores	Godot
P26	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Console	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity
P27	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unreal, Godot

P28	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games, Simulators	Mobile devices, Computer, Augmented reality, VR	Digital download stores	Unity
P29	Entertainment games	Computer	Digital download stores	Blender, Godot, Pygame
P30	Entertainment games, Educational games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Godot
P31	Entertainment games, Educational games	Computer, Browsers	Digital download stores, Own website, Online gaming portals	Godot, melonJS
P32	Entertainment games, Educational games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity, Godot
P33	Entertainment games	Computer	Digital download stores	Godot
P34	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games, Advergaming, Simulators, Games for well-being	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console, Augmented reality	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity
P35	Entertainment games, working with outsourcing to other studios (Concept art, Illustration, Visual Identity, UX/UI, etc.)	Computer	Publishers, Digital Download Stores: We haven't yet launched our main product; it will be available in digital download stores in partnership with publishers.	Unity
P36	Entertainment games	Computer	Digital download stores, Own website, Online gaming portals	Unreal
P37	Entertainment games	Computer, Console	Publishers, Digital Download Stores	Construct, Game Maker Studio 2
P38	Entertainment games, Advergaming	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity

P39	Entertainment games, Educational games	Computer, Browsers	Own website, Online gaming portals	Unity, Unreal, Construct, Godot
P40	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	RPG Maker
P41	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Physical card game.	Own website	Unity
P42	Educational games, Corporate training games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Direct-to-consumer sales	Unity, Construct, Tecnologia própria, Renpy
P43	Entertainment games	Computador, Console	Digital download stores	Unreal
P44	Entertainment games, Simulators	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Own website, Online gaming portals	Unity, Blender
P45	Educational games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Customer-authored platform	Unity, Godot, HTML5
P46	Entertainment games	Computer, Console	Digital download stores, Own website, Online gaming portals	Unity
P47	Entertainment games	Mobile devices	Mobile app stores	Unity, Blender, Godot, Own technology
P48	Entertainment games	Computer	Digital download stores	Unity
P49	Entertainment games, Advergames	Mobile devices, Computer, Console	The company works with outsourcing, so the client is responsible for distribution.	Unity, Unreal
P50	Entertainment games, Educational games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Publishers, Digital download stores, Online gaming portals	Unity
P51	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Own website, Online gaming portals	Unity

P52	Entertainment games, instant games	Mobile devices, Browsers, Discord, Facebook	Publishers, Own website, Discord, Facebook	Own technology
P53	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Digital download stores, Online gaming portals	Unity, Unreal
P54	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity
P55	Entertainment games	Computer	Publishers, Digital Download Stores	Unity
P56	Entertainment games	VR	Publishers	Unreal
P57	Entertainment games	VR	Digital download stores	Unity, Unreal
P58	Entertainment games, Educational games	Mobile devices, Computer, Virtual Reality	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity
P59	Entertainment games	Computer, Console	Publishers, Digital Download Stores	Game Maker
P60	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer	Publishers	Unity
P61	Educational games, Gamified apps for education	Mobile devices, Browsers	Digital download stores	Unity
P62	Entertainment games, Educational games, Simulators	Mobile devices, Computers, Browsers, Augmented reality	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity, Unreal
P63	I literally play every type of game (without restrictions).	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console	Publishers, own website, online gaming portals – I'm not the one who oversees this, but from the projects I've worked on, this was the format.	Unity, Construct, Blender, Aseprite and Krita
P64	Entertainment games, Educational games, Advergames	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity, Construct, Blender

P65	Entertainment games	Mobile devices	Mobile app stores	Unity, Blender
P66	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Browsers	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity
P67	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer	Publishers, Mobile app stores, Own website	Unity, Unreal
P68	Entertainment games	VR and Mixed VR	Digital download stores	Unity, Unreal
P69	Entertainment games	Mobile devices	Mobile app stores	Unity
P70	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity, Blender, Aseprite, Adobe Illustrator
P71	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games, Advergames	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console, Augmented reality	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity, Godot, Cocos Creator
P72	Entertainment games	Computer, Console	First game, distribution hasn't started yet.	Unity, Unreal, Own technology
P73	Entertainment games	Computer	We haven't published any games yet, but we plan to release them on Steam.	Unity
P74	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games, Advergames	Mobile devices, Computer, Console, Augmented reality	Publishers	Unity
P75	Entertainment games	Mobile devices	Mobile app stores	Unity
P76	Entertainment games	Computer, Browsers	Own website, Online gaming portals	Unity
P77	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console, Augmented reality	Publishers	Unity, Unreal, Own technology
P78	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity

P79	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Console, Augmented reality	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Own website, Online gaming portals	N/A
P80	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer	Publishers, Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity, Unreal
P81	Entertainment games	Computer	Publishers, Digital Download Stores	Unreal
P82	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games, Simulators	Mobile devices, Computers, Browsers, Consoles, Augmented reality, Any emerging tech	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity, Unreal, Godot, Tecnologia própria, Frostbite
P83	Entertainment games, Corporate training games	Computer, Console	Digital download stores	Unity
P84	Entertainment games	Computer, Console	Publishers	Unreal
P85	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console	Digital download stores	Unity, Unreal, Godot
P86	Entertainment games, Advergames	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console, Augmented reality	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity, Unreal
P87	Entertainment games, Corporate training games, Advergames	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity, Unreal, Godot, Roblox
P88	Entertainment games	Computer	Own website	Unity, Blender
P89	Entertainment games	Computer, Console	Digital download stores, Online gaming portals	Unreal
P90	Entertainment games, Advergames	Computer, Browsers	Online gaming portals	Construct, Godot

P91	Entertainment games, Advergimes	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Mobile app stores, Own website, Online gaming portals	Unity, Unreal, Godot
P92	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games, Simulators, Games for health	Mobile devices, Computers, Browsers, Augmented reality	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity, Unreal, Construct, Blender, Godot, Threejs, Pixijs, Roblox
P93	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer	Digital download stores	Unity
P94	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console, Augmented reality	These are games commissioned by clients; distribution is their responsibility.	Unity, Construct
P95	Entertainment games	Computer	We haven't reached the distribution phase yet.	Unreal, own Technology
P96	Entertainment games, Educational games, Advergimes	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Publishers, Mobile app stores	Unity, Game Maker
P97	Entertainment games, Simulators	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console	Doesn't distribute the game; she only does part of the work (they outsource a part of the game to us, like a feature, or a mobile port, for example). The publishers are the ones who distribute it.	Unity, Unreal
P98	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Own website, Online gaming portals	Unity, Unreal
P99	Entertainment games, Educational games, Advergimes, Games for health	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity, Godot

P100	Entertainment games	Computer	Publishers	Unity, Unreal
P101	Entertainment games	Computer	Online gaming portals	Unity
P102	Entertainment games, Advergames	Mobile devices, Computer	Digital download stores	Unity, Unreal
P103	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Console	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity
P104	Entertainment games	Computer, Browsers	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Own website, Online gaming portals	Unity, Construct, Godot, RenPy, Twine
P105	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity, Construct, Godot
P106	Entertainment games, Educational games, Advergames	Mobile devices, Computer	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity, Construct
P107	It's usually more personal projects; I don't have much access to the games I've worked on.	Computer	Own website	Unity
P108	Entertainment games	Computer	Digital download stores	Unity
P109	Does not develop games.	Does not develop games.	Does not develop games.	N/A
P110	Entertainment games	Computer	We haven't published a game yet.	Unity
P111	Educational games, Games for health	Computer	Own website	Unity, Godot
P112	Entertainment games, Educational games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity, Cocos Creator
P113	Entertainment games, Educational games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity
P114	Educational games	Mobile devices, Computer	Own website	Godot

P115	Entertainment games	Mobile devices	Mobile app stores	Unity, Blender
P116	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Console	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Own website	Unity
P117	Entertainment games	All	Because my work is outsourced, I don't have information on how each game is published.	Unity, Unreal, Godot,
P118	Entertainment games	Computer	For now, I have no plans; I'm doing freelance work.	Unity
P119	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computers, Browsers, Augmented reality	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Online gaming portals	Unity
P120	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity
P121	Corporate training games, Simulators	Mobile devices, Browsers, Augmented reality	Own website	Unity, Blender
P122	Educational games	Mobile devices, Computer	Internal events	Unity
P123	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Own website, Online gaming portals	Unity
P124	Entertainment games, Educational games, Advergaming, Games for well-being, Serious games	Mobile devices, Computer, Browsers, Console	Digital download stores, Mobile app stores, Own website, Online gaming portals	Unity, Godot, lua
P125	Entertainment games	Mobile devices, Computer, Console	Own website, Online gaming portals	Unreal
P126	Entertainment games	Computer	Digital download stores	Unreal
P127	Entertainment games, Educational games	Mobile devices, Board game	Mobile app stores, Own website	Unity, Construct

P128	Entertainment games, Educational games, Corporate training games, Advergaming	Mobile devices, Computers, Browsers, Augmented reality	Publishers, Digital download stores, Mobile app stores	Unity	
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